

REALIZATION OF FIBER STRENGTH IN A UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITE

Vitauts Tamužs

(Institute of Polymer Mechanics, Riga, Latvia, U.S.S.R)

Fracture of unidirectional composites containing brittle fibers under tension takes place by non-correlative accumulation of breaks of separate fibers in the initial stage of loading. When a certain level of breaks has been achieved either the development of the macrocrack takes place or the broken fibers are pulled out of the matrix and the sample splits into separate parts. It is common knowledge that the so called critical length of a fiber, that is, the smallest possible length of the segments a fiber can split into until it is pulled out of the matrix, is determined by fiber strength, adhesion, deformational and geometrical parameters of the composite constituents. Maximally attainable composite strength is determined by the mean fiber strength $\langle \sigma \rangle$ at the critical length l_e and the coefficient of volume fraction v_f :

$$\sigma_k^l = \langle \sigma \rangle v_f.$$

There is a well known approximate expression for

$$l_e = \frac{\sigma d}{2\tilde{z}} \quad (1)$$

where \tilde{z} —the magnitude of adhesion, d —the fiber diameter, σ —the stress in the fiber at the moment of breaking, that is, the fiber strength at the length l_e . So the mean magnitude $\langle l_e \rangle$ is determined by the mean magnitude $\langle \sigma \rangle$ at the length $\langle l_e \rangle$

$$\langle l_e \rangle = \frac{\langle \sigma \rangle d}{2\tilde{z}}. \quad (2)$$

This dependence can be used if the value $\langle \sigma(l_e) \rangle$ is known. It can be obtained by extrapolating the scale dependence $\langle \sigma(l) \rangle$ at the length l_e .

The modified Weibul distribution of the fiber strength has the following form¹

$$F(\sigma) = 1 - \exp \left[\left(-\frac{l}{l_0} \right)^\alpha \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0} \right)^\beta \right]. \quad (3)$$

It leads to the expression for the mean strength.

$$\langle \sigma \rangle = \sigma_0 \left(\frac{l}{l_0} \right)^{-\frac{\alpha}{\beta}} \Gamma \left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta} \right) \quad (4)$$

or

$$\lg \langle \sigma(\ell) \rangle = A - B \lg \frac{\ell}{\ell_0} \quad (5)$$

where

$$A = \lg \langle \sigma(\ell_0) \rangle, \quad B = \frac{\alpha}{\beta}. \quad (6)$$

The expression (5) fits the experimental data very well².

Formulas for the maximally attainable fiber strength in the composite $\langle \sigma \rangle = \langle \sigma(\ell_e) \rangle$ and the critical length ℓ_e follow from expressions (5) and (2) simply.

$$\begin{aligned} \lg \langle \sigma \rangle &= \frac{1}{1+B} \left(A - B \lg \frac{d}{\ell_0} + B \lg 2\bar{z} \right), \\ \lg \ell_e &= \frac{1}{1+B} \left(A + \lg \frac{d}{\ell_0} - \lg 2\bar{z} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

The real fiber strength in the composite σ_r , however, makes only a part of the maximally attainable : $\sigma_r = k \langle \sigma \rangle, k < 1$ because the propagation of the macrocrack takes place in the composite as soon as the number of crumbs reaches a few per cents or even less than a per cent out of the maximally attainable amount of breaks. The dependence

$$\lg \sigma_r = \lg k + \frac{1}{1+B} \left(A - B \lg \frac{d}{\ell_0} + B \lg 2\bar{z} \right) \quad (8)$$

can be used in order to forecast the composite strength and to optimize it if the magnitudes A, B, d, \bar{z}, k are known. The coefficient of the fiber strength realization k is the function of the fiber volume v_f , the relation of the modulus of the fiber elasticity E_f to the modulus of the matrix elasticity E_m , and it depends also on the statistical parameters of the fiber strength distribution (3). This dependence can be obtained by a theoretical calculation of the stress concentration in the vicinity of the fiber break, but it can be acquired for a certain group of composites empirically⁴.

In order to find $k(v_f, B, E_f)$ for cfrp composites the samples with voluminous fiber content $0.5 < v_f < 0.75$ were tested under three-point bending. It turned out that in the given range of v_f the k decreased linearly with the increase of v_f (Fig.1).

Fig. 1. Scale dependences of strength (a) and dependences of the realization factor k on filler content (b) for CF fillers with different values of E_f and B ; 1) $E_f = 23.5$ ton-f/mm² and $B = 0.188$; 2) 35.0 and 0.079; 3) 19.5 and 0.176.

When testing composites containing various fibers that differed in the magnitude B , it was discovered that the coefficient of proportionality $k(v_f)$ changed linearly depending on B so that a

sufficiently reliable empirical dependence has the form

$$k = \alpha(B, E) - 3.8Bv_f$$

The strength and, correspondingly, the coefficient of realization k were investigated for fibers with alterations of the modulus of fibers $1,95 \cdot 10^5 \text{ MPa} < E_f < 4,15 \cdot 10^5 \text{ MPa}$ at $v_f = 0.6$ and the same matrix $E_m = 3 \cdot 10^3 \text{ MPa}$. It turned out that the coefficient of realization decreased linearly with the increase of the fiber stiffness, besides, the coefficient of proportionality depended on B linearly again (Fig. 2,3).

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 2. Dependence of k on B for CF fillers with different elastic moduli at $v_f = 0.6$; $E_f = 19.5(1)$; $23.5(2)$; $26.3(3)$; $34.7(4)$; $35.0(5)$; $41.5(6)$.

Fig.3. Dependence of the slope tangent of the straight lines in Fig. 2 on the elastic modulus of CF fillers at $v_f = 0.6$.

The final empirical dependence $k(\frac{E_f}{E_m}, v_f, B)$ for carbon fibers and the epoxy-phenol matrix can be presumed in the form⁴

$$k = 1 - B(0.036 \frac{E_f}{E_m} + 3.8 v_f - 2.9). \quad (9)$$

Specimens of composites to check (9) were made on the basis of the carbon fibers T-H and the epoxy-phenol matrix. Properties of these fibers, determined according to⁵, are presented in Table 1.

The adhesion value $\tilde{z} = 7.92$ was obtained by means of shear test. According to (7), the maximally attainable strength $\langle \sigma \rangle$ was determined, the values of k, σ_r^T were calculated after (9), (8) (Table 2). When the composite specimens based on T-H were tested under bending, it gave $\sigma^e = 221 \text{ kgf/mm}^2$. This outcome agrees with the calculated value σ^T well.

Table 1. Properties of CF Fillers T-H

Substance	σ (10mm) kgf/mm ²	df_1/cm	$E_f t/mm^2$	A	B
T-H	447	6.60	30.0	2.7578	0.120

Table 2. Properties of the Composites

Substance	\bar{z} kgf/mm ²	$\langle \sigma \rangle$ kgf/mm ²	v_f	k	σ_r^T	σ^T	σ^e
T-H	7.9	668	0.49	0.689	460	224	221

As it is seen from (8) and (9) the composite strength is determined by the scale dependence of the fiber strength essentially expressed by the coefficient B and that is the consequence of the statistical distribution of fiber strength. In the paper¹ and, later, in the works of other scientists there was stated the applicability of the modified Weibul distribution (3), and the value of parameter α was estimated ≈ 0.5 for all the tested carbon fibers. The magnitude of $B = \frac{\alpha}{\beta}$ can be stated using two methods - either testing separate microfibers with different lengths or recording breaks of fibers in the composite or especially prepared microplastics⁵. The latter method has certain advantages because it presumes studies of the fiber strength distribution when in contact with the matrix and it is less labor-consuming. However, in order to carry out the method, it is necessary to have the equipment for recording the signals of acoustic emission from the break of separate fibers. The analysis of the obtained information on accumulation of breaks in the microplastics is based on the fact that the fracture of a unidirectional composite takes place under stress $\sigma_r = k\langle \sigma \rangle < \langle \sigma \rangle$. As follows from (4) then $\sigma < \sigma_0$ and (3) permits asymptotic expansion:

$$F(\sigma) \approx (\sigma/\sigma_*)^\beta \tag{10}$$

where

$$\sigma_* = \sigma_0 \left(\frac{\ell_0}{\ell} \right)^{\frac{\alpha}{\beta}} \tag{11}$$

Virtually (10) means that only the left side of the Weibul distribution or the modified Weibul distribution (3) is essential. The formula (10) is expressed as a straight line in the double logarithmic coordinates:

$$\lg F(\sigma) = \beta \lg \sigma - \beta \lg \sigma_* \tag{12}$$

According to (3) the function $0 < P(\sigma) < 1$, consequently, it is possible to interpret it as a relative number of the fiber breaks in the composite:

$$F(\sigma) = N(\sigma)/N_0 \tag{13}$$

where $N(\sigma)$ - the number of observed breaks, N_0 - maximally attainable amount of breaks in the specimen. It follows from (12) and (13)

$$\lg N(\sigma) = \lg(N_0) - \beta \lg \sigma_* + \beta \lg \sigma \tag{14}$$

Formula (14) permits to find β and σ_* after the measured values σ and $N(\sigma)$. The value β that is determined by the angle of the slope of the straight line $\lg(N) \sim \lg(\sigma)$ does not depend on N_0 ; the value σ_* and, correspondingly, σ_0 from (11) can be found only then if N_0 is known, that means, the number of all the possible fiber breaks in the composite (microplastics):

$$N_0 = \frac{LM}{\ell_e} \tag{15}$$

where L - the length of the specimen, M - the number of fibers in the specimen, ℓ_e - the critical length. It is possible to get the dependence from (01), (11) and (13) as well

$$\sigma_0 = \left(\frac{N_0}{N} \right)^{\frac{1}{\beta}} \left(\frac{\ell}{\ell_0} \right)^{\frac{\alpha}{\beta}} \sigma \tag{16}$$

and, taking into account that length of fibers in the composite should be taken $\ell = \ell_c$ we get finally

$$\sigma_0 = \left(\frac{N_0}{N}\right)^{\frac{1}{\beta}} \left(\frac{\ell_c}{\ell_0}\right)^{\frac{\alpha}{\beta}} \sigma. \quad (17)$$

In order to get the mean fiber strength at the length ℓ , (8) and (17) are used:

$$\langle \sigma(\ell) \rangle = \left(\frac{N_0}{N}\right)^{\frac{1}{\beta}} \left(\frac{\ell_c}{\ell}\right)^{\frac{\alpha}{\beta}} \sigma \Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta}\right). \quad (18)$$

The expectable mean strength at the critical length

$$\langle \sigma(\ell_c) \rangle = \left(\frac{N_0}{N}\right)^{\frac{1}{\beta}} \sigma \Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta}\right). \quad (19)$$

Different sorts of fibers and microplastics were tested as samples. The typical dependence $\lg N \sim \lg \sigma$ for fibers T-300 is represented in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. The number of acoustic emission events versus stress at microplastic tension.

The lower part of the graph (first hundred signals approximately) is determined by the conditions under which the experiment is carried out and it does not characterize the qualities of fibers. The fracture of fibers starts at a certain level of stress $\sigma \approx 0.5 \div 0.7 \sigma_{\min}$ and the angle of the slope of the straight line $\beta = 5.86$ agrees with the value of the Weibul distribution parameter obtained when testing fibers directly. In order to state the scale dependence of strength there is necessity, however, to take into account the coefficient $\alpha \approx 0.5$ where from $B = 0.085$ for the given type of fibers.

REFERENCES

1. Gutans Yu.A., Tamužs V.P., *Mekhanika kompozitnih materialov*, (6) (1984), 1107–1109.
2. Tamužs V.P., Azarova M.T. and others, *Mekhanika kompozitnih materialov*, (1) (1982), 34–41.
3. Korabelnikov Yu.G., Tamužs V.P. and others, *Mekhanika kompozitnih materialov*, (2) (1984), 195–200.
4. Korabelnikov Yu.G., Siluyanov O.F., Tamužs V.P. and others, *Mekhanika kompozitnih materialov*, (2) (1987), 270–274.
5. Tamužs V.P., Protasov V.D., *Fracture of Composite Material Structures*, (1986), p. 264 (in Russian).